

EFFECT OF STRESS-PROTECTIVE THERAPY ON THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF TOTAL PERIPHERAL VASCULAR RESISTANCE IN PATIENTS WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN

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Abstract. *A comparative analysis of the average parameters of the circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) in the acute period of severe combined traumatic brain injury (STBI) in children over 7 years old revealed no significant differences. During stress-protective pharmacological treatment, a wave-like change in total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) was noted, more pronounced in children of Group 1, within the range of 1200–1700 dyn·s·cm⁻⁵ during the first 17 days, following an approximately weekly rhythm. In Group 2, fluctuations in TPVR during the first ten days occurred within 700–1100 dyn·s·cm⁻⁵. Variations in the amplitude of the circadian rhythm of TPVR indicated somewhat more pronounced centralization of blood circulation on day 1 in children of Group 2. A near-weekly rhythm in changes of TPVR circadian rhythm amplitude was observed in both groups. In both groups, an inverse correlation between TPVR and cardiac output (CO) was identified: in Group 1 (-0.8), in Group 2 (-0.9), characteristic of a stress response involving hyperdynamic hemodynamic adaptation.*

Keywords: *stress-limiting therapy, circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance, children, severe combined traumatic brain injury.*

Introduction.

Disruption of circadian rhythms has become more common in society due to the increasing number of shift workers, sleep disturbances, exposure to blue light, and travel across time zones. Severe combined trauma (SCT) is the most dangerous type of injury, characterized by prolonged disability with a high level of impairment and mortality, ten times higher than that of isolated injuries. Autonomic regulation disorders are among the leading, and often the only, clinical manifestations in both the acute and long-term periods of mild traumatic brain injury.

Systemic consequences of traumatic brain injury manifest as extracranial multi-organ dysfunction (MOD), which occurs in over 68% of patients with moderate to severe TBI within the first 72 hours of hospitalization. Dysfunction of extracranial organs can create a vicious cycle that exacerbates further brain injury. Autonomic dysfunction has been shown to be an important factor in the development of MOD after TBI, particularly in severe cases. This dysfunction triggers a cascade of physiological disturbances affecting multiple extracranial organ systems, including the respiratory, cardiovascular, renal, and coagulation systems.

The development of traumatic brain disease is accompanied not only by structural-functional changes in the CNS but also by a complex of pathophysiological shifts occurring in nearly all organs and systems of the body. It has been established that the reorganization of

functional regulatory mechanisms during stress depends on the individual typological characteristics of the child, with the sympathectomy type of autonomic regulation being the least adaptive, leading to a less favorable prognosis for recovery of organ and system function.

Using a systems approach, typological features of the interaction of homeostatic mechanisms in blood flow, hematopoiesis, immunity, and hemostasis have been studied in school-age children. Previous studies by the authors confirmed that the severity of brain injury affects the hemodynamic state in children with STBI. A characteristic feature of shock in pediatric SCT is a tendency for rapid shifts from hemodynamic compensation to decompensation and deepening of shock.

Experimental evidence shows that severe TBI is accompanied by depressed myocardial contractility and increased myocardial dependence on oxygen and glucose, likely related to pathogenic factors such as hypoxia, bioenergetic dysfunction, oxidative stress, and Ca^{2+} imbalance.

However, there is still insufficient information regarding changes in myocardial oxygen demand, disruption of the circadian rhythm of myocardial oxygen demand (MOD), and cardiac function in compensatory hemodynamic responses in children with STBI. The pathogenetic and etiological roles of cardiac function disorders in the development of multi-organ failure syndrome (MOFS) remain poorly understood, significantly complicating the development of comprehensive intensive therapy for this patient population.

Objective. To study the influence of stress-protective therapy on the circadian rhythm of total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR) in children over 7 years old with severe combined traumatic brain injury (sTBI).

Materials and Methods. The study included 20 children aged 7.1 to 18 years who were treated in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care (RSC EMC) at the 2nd Children's Clinical Hospital in Tashkent. Group 1 consisted of children admitted between 2018 and 2022. Group 2 included children with STBI admitted between 2023 and 2024.

Upon admission to the ICU, all patients underwent a comprehensive diagnostic assessment, including biochemical blood analysis and complete blood count, evaluation of coagulation potential, and, as indicated, chest X-rays and X-rays of fracture sites. All patients underwent computed tomography (CT) of the head.

Non-invasive continuous monitoring with hourly registration of parameters in the ICU included measurement of blood oxygen saturation, heart rate (HR), and mean arterial pressure (MAP). Parameters of central hemodynamics were also measured. The primary goal of intensive therapy in severe TBI was to support compromised vital functions and create conditions for the maximal possible recovery of brain function.

During 2018-2022, components of intensive complex therapy were studied in 10 children (Group 1) aged 7.1–18 years. A comparative analysis was conducted with a similar group of 10 children (Group 2) in 2023–2024, matched for diagnosis, age, and severity of condition. Data were processed using variation statistics with Microsoft Excel by calculating arithmetic means (M) and standard errors of the mean (m). To assess the significance of differences between two values, the student's t-test was used. Relationships between the dynamics of the studied parameters were determined using the method of paired correlations. The critical significance level was set at 0.05.

Results and Discussion. Comparative analysis of the average parameters of the circadian rhythm of TPVR in the acute period of STBI in children over 7 years revealed no significant differences (Table 1).

Table 1. Average values of the phase structure of the circadian rhythm of TPVR ($\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$)

Groups	Mesor	In acrophase	Bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily Range
1	1300±132	1762±286	1008±126	462±203	754±282
2	1073±115	1486±276	823±64	413±215	663±272

Table 2. Dynamics of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of TPVR ($\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$)

Table 3. Average circadian rhythm of TPVR ($\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$)

Hours	Group 1	Group 2
8	1300±210	1033±152
9	1309±179	1042±165
10	1264±185	1053±132
1	1271±191	1043±163
12	1260±205	1055±175
13	1325±263	1098±210
14	1355±298	1077±164
15	1326±244	1022±156
16	1215±169	1030±166
17	1267±176	1042±134
18	1376±273	1108±170
19	1355±199	1109±181
20	1310±205	1102±178
21	1309±213	1062±167
22	1271±173	1081±156
23	1286±142	1038±121
24	1307±123	1114±182
1	1276±155	1067±191
2	1294±147	1105±204
3	1335±194	1103±165
4	1359±182	1061±158
5	1296±162	1123±145
6	1263±167	1094±196
7	1281±199	1089±191

Days	Group 1	Group 2
1	1760±501	1001±281
2	1214±79	755±78
3	1196±63	843±67
4	1265±73	940±60
5	1387±69	1055±63
6	1340±56	1015±106
7	1313±52	1005±78
8	1189±72	1116±169
9	1602±177	1011±92
10	1223±81	1083±150
11	1280±125	1056±138
12	1379±140	978±80
13	1541±140	944±108
14	1575±152	1037±92
15	1219±90	989±103
16	1189±134	951±64
17	1287±119	1010±104
18	1603±295	999±88
19	1125±102	1108±96
20	1252±145	1175±123
21	1294±189	1290±212
22	1070±138	1336±165
23	1201±133	1125±149
24	1058±97	1354±252
25	1250±189	1169±147
26	1296±278	983±97
27	1038±136	1346±194
28	1144±185	1192±185
29	1422±232	1240±97

A tendency for an increase in TPVR was observed on the first day in traumatized children of Group 1 (Table 2). In the following days, a wave-like change in TPVR was noted, more pronounced in children of Group 1, ranging from 1200–1700 $\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$ during the first 17 days, following an approximately weekly rhythm. In Group 2, TPVR fluctuations during the first ten days ranged from 700–1100 $\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$. However, no statistically significant dynamics of the mesor of the TPVR circadian rhythm were detected in either group of patients (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the mesor of the TPVR circadian rhythm ($\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$)

Figure 2. Average circadian rhythm of TPVR (dyn·s·cm⁻⁵)

Fluctuations in TPVR within the average circadian rhythm occurred in Group 1 within the range of 1210–1370 dyn·s·cm⁻⁵, and in Group 2 at the level of 1020–1120 dyn·s·cm⁻⁵. Thus, the difference in the mesors of the TPVR circadian rhythm, depending on the type of pharmacological protection, was approximately 300 dyn·s·cm⁻⁵, indicating more effective correction in patients of Group 2.

Figure 3. Amplitude of TPVR fluctuations in the circadian rhythm (dyn·s·cm⁻⁵)

Fluctuations in the amplitude of the TPVR circadian rhythm indicated a somewhat more pronounced centralization of blood circulation on day 1 in children of Group 2. A near-weekly rhythm in changes of TPVR circadian rhythm amplitude was observed in both groups (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Dynamics of the daily range of TPVR changes (dyn·s·cm⁻⁵)

This is confirmed by the dynamics of daily TPVR fluctuations in a near-weekly rhythm (Figure 4) in both groups of children. In both groups, an inverse correlation between TPVR and cardiac output (CO) was observed: -0.8 in Group 1 and -0.9 in Group 2, characteristic of a stress-induced hyperdynamic hemodynamic response. However, the tendency in Group 1 for stroke volume (SV) to decrease with increasing TPVR (-0.7) was less pronounced in Group 2 (-0.5).

In Group 1, increases in diastolic arterial pressure (DAP) corresponded to increases in TPVR (0.8), along with simultaneous increases in systolic arterial pressure (SAP) (0.7). An increase in anti-inflammatory therapy was associated with a decrease in TPVR (-0.9). In children, the tendency for TPVR to decrease was also influenced by an increase in daily infusion volume (-0.4), mainly via the enteral route (-0.5).

Figure 5. Duration of inversion of the TPVR circadian rhythm

No significant differences were found in the duration of inversion of the TPVR circadian rhythm, which was 43% in Group 1 and 46% in Group 2 of the total duration of intensive therapy in the ICU (Figure 5).

Conclusion. Comparative analysis of the average parameters of the TPVR circadian rhythm in the acute period of STBI in children over 7 years revealed no significant differences. During stress-protective pharmacological therapy, a wave-like change in TPVR was observed, more pronounced in children of Group 1, ranging from 1200–1700 $\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$ during the first 17 days, following an approximately weekly rhythm. In Group 2, TPVR fluctuations during the first ten days ranged from 700–1100 $\text{dyn}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{cm}^{-5}$. Fluctuations in the amplitude of the TPVR circadian rhythm indicated a somewhat more pronounced centralization of blood circulation on day 1 in children of Group 2. A near-weekly rhythm in changes of TPVR circadian rhythm amplitude was observed in both groups. In both groups, an inverse correlation between TPVR and cardiac output (CO) was identified: -0.8 in Group 1 and -0.9 in Group 2, characteristic of a stress-induced hyperdynamic hemodynamic response.

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